

THE NAGATIVE AND POSITIVE IMPACTS OF COVID-19 TO THE TOURISM INDUSTRY OF AUSTRIA

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Executive summary

This report provides information on the technological, social, and technological damage caused to the Austrian tourism industry during the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, the following sections show what problems existed in the above three aspects and what measures were taken by the government to address them. That is why the Austrian government has tried and succeeded in creating specific measures for tourism, in addition to the measures that are common throughout the world during the global pandemic.

In addition, statistical aspect tables of how much Austria has spent on tourism development during the pandemic are demonstrated in this report. The economic effect part, for example, discusses the government's financial status before the epidemic, how many visitors visited Austria's landmarks and historical sites and how they benefitted society, as well as how much revenue they brought into the economy.

Furthermore, what issues were experienced with visitors during the subsequent social part pandemic, and restrictions were enforced on them to visit Austria once the quarantine measures were removed, as well as the influence of tourists on them. That seems to be, they will be obliged to acquire a vaccination and show proof of it before entering Austrian territory, and statistics on how many individuals have been vaccinated will also be supplied.

Finally, the research discusses the single technologically favorable influence on Austrian tourism. That seems to be, it demonstrates the location of IT equipment developed during the epidemic and so now, as well as the efficacy of their actual use.

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Introduction

In the beginning, the coronavirus continues to spread globally, now being officially recognized as a pandemic by the WHO. The eventual economic impact of the coronavirus on the Austrian economy cannot be predicted due to the disease's uncertain progression. However, a glance at the industries impacted and the safeguards put in place so far offers an idea of the virus's potential impact on the economy. The tourism and entertainment industry plays an important role in Austria's economy, and we analyze the technological and social effects of the aforementioned aspects on the chosen sector.

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According to the current economy of Austria, Austria's GDP increased by 3.8 percent in the third quarter of 2021 compared to the previous quarter, and the total GDP was 429 billion USD. Austria's GDP increased by 3.8 percent in the third quarter of 2021 compared to the previous quarter. This rate is four-tenths of a percentage point lower than that of the 4.2 percent published in the second quarter of 2021. (The Worldometer, 2021)

Besides, with its spectacular castles, most of which were built during the Habsburg era, Baroque castles and gardens, and ruins and monuments going back to the Middle Ages, and 30.8 million travelers visited Austria in 2018. Tourism is a significant element of the Austrian economy, accounting for over 9% of the gross domestic product of the country. Austria ranked ninth in the world in international tourist earnings in 2007, with 18.9 billion US dollars. (The Department of Austria, 2019)

In general, the main goal of this report is to find out which areas of Austria were damaged as a result of Covid 19, their causes, the state of tourism before and after the pandemic, their prevention methods, and their effectiveness.

Findings and Analysis

Economic Impact

To begin with, given the impact of tourism on the economy before the COVID 19 pandemic in Austria, in absolute terms, Austria ranked 20th in the world with 32 million tourists in 2019. (WorldData, 2019) It is evident that smaller countries consistently do worse when compared to the absolute quantity of visitors than large economies compared to high generated states. When tourist numbers are compared to Austria's population, the picture becomes much more comparable,

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Austria ranked 34th in the world with 3.6 visitors per citizen. (Statista, 2019) It was ranked second in Western Europe. Vienna is the most popular destination for foreign visitors in Austria with 6.63 million visitors in 2019, it ranked 39th among the world's most visited cities. Each visitor that arrived in 2019 spent an average of USD 694. When it comes to trips overseas, Austrians can spend up to \$1,018 each year.

The graph below shows the number of tourists visiting Austria over the years compared to other Western Europe.

(WorldData.info, 2019)

As for the share of tourism in Austria's GDP, the active and passive value-added of Austria's tourist industry was anticipated to be around 20.5 billion euros in 2020, a significant decrease from the previous year owing to the impact of the coronavirus pandemic. (New York Times, 2020) The actual benefit of this industry to the Austrian economy reached more than 29.7 billion euros in 2019.

The graph below shows the contribution you are making to the tourism industry in Austria's GDP.

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(Statista, 2021)

As a result of the pandemic, the unemployment rate in the Austrian labor market has risen, which has had a significant negative impact on the economy. The number of unemployed persons registered with the Public Employment Services (PES) reached a new high in March and April. Since about the end of the lockdown in May, the job situation has progressively improved. In September, unemployment was almost 22% higher than in the same month the previous year and decreased from almost 60 percent in April.

Furthermore, the percentage of workers enrolled with the short-term employment plan has dropped by 70% from its high in the spring. (Institute of Labor Economics, 2020) In March of this year, the national unemployment rate increased by 4.7 percentage points to 12.2 percent. The government plans to do "everything it takes, whatever it requires" to minimize the socioeconomic impacts of the COVID-19 problem, which would total upwards of 10% of Austrian GDP. (Velina Tchakarova, 2020)

The line graph below shows Austria's unemployment rate for the years following the pandemic.

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(Statista. 2021)

Social Impact

During COVID-19, Austria, like all governments, was forced to restrict various social activities, and the United Nations split the virus's influence into the following areas: older persons, Persons with Disabilities, Youth, Families, Indigenous peoples, and Sport for Development and Peace. UN research shows that occurred situation of the older person during the pandemic, older people, particularly those with chronic health disorders such as cholesterol, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes, are especially vulnerable to COVID-19 infection. (United Nations, 2020) Not only do older people face increased health risks, but they are also more likely to be incapable of sustaining themselves in solitude.

Although social isolation is required to limit illness spread, if not handled effectively, such efforts might lead to increasing social isolation of elderly people at a time even though they need the help of assistance. Though in the best of circumstances, people with disabilities encounter barriers to

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health-care services owing to a lack of availability, accessibility, and price, as well as stigma and prejudice.

The risks of COVID-19 virus for people with disabilities are exacerbated by other issues that necessitate specific action, such as disruption of support and services, pre-existing health conditions in some cases that put them at greater risk of developing serious illness or dying, being excluded from health information and mainstream health provision, growing up in a world where availability is often constrained and obstacles to goods and services are a struggle, and being discriminated against. (BBC News, 2021)

Furthermore, one of the most serious social issues in Austria was the absence of crowds and special events throughout the three waves of the COVID-19 epidemic, since only food and other medical difficulties were permitted. (New York Times, 2021)

The table below illustrates how many Austrians are presently immunized against Covid 19.

(Covidvax.live, 2021)

Technological Impact

COVID-19 had a detrimental impact on many sectors of Austria, but it had a more favorable impact on the technological side of Austrian tourism during the epidemic. As we all know, travel to other countries was halted during the pandemic, and as a result, tourist countries such as Austria were able to see the countries that tourists wanted to visit at home in the online 3D format of historical places, based on equipment controlled by special "Artificial Intelligence," but anyway "Cloud computing" systems were created and are actively used. (SpringerLink, 2020)

The table given below demonstrates that Cloud service providers' use of cloud computing services among travel companies, tour operators, and associated activities in the European Union between 2016 and 2020.

(Statista info, 2021)

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Furthermore, once quarantine was loosened, unique remote temperature monitoring equipment was devised to determine the body temperature of visitors visiting Austria, and they became the major working instrument of the Austrian tourism sector. Traveling more quickly, safely, and effectively has fueled the development of groundbreaking technology solutions that serve the main purpose of people. (BBC, 2021)

During the pandemic, accommodation and transportation providers have significantly increased their options for contactless and mobile check-in, which helps to establish visitor trust across the board by decreasing shared touchpoints and interpersonal contacts. Hotels, amusement parks, airports, and railway stations have developed dedicated mobile applications that allow consumers to easily check-in, purchase, and pay for a service on their devices. (Travel Pulse, 2021)

For 3D visualization by the Austrian government to promote tourism of "House of Digitalization" project is EUR 1 201 806 with the EU's European Regional Development Fund investing EUR 1 201 806 under the Operational Program "Investments in Growth and Employment Austria" for the 2014-2020 programming period. (European Commission, 2020) Simultaneously, special delivery and courier services were established to maintain the health of tourists visiting Austria long after the pandemic was alleviated, which aided in the development of services not before accessible to the state, and the most popular of these are "Heavy Pedals", "MG-Botendienst", "Transport - Michael Klemm" and others. (Wiley Online Library, 2019)

Conclusion

Overall, the COVID-19 epidemic has had an economic, social, and, of course, technical impact on Austria, which has been both detrimental and good in various aspects. Tourism has struggled the most, as indicated by the examples and data above, as tourism is Austria's primary business and plays a significant role in the country's economy.

According to the facts presented in the preceding sections of Austria, such as the rest of Europe, was unable to find a solution owing to a lack of expertise to prevent it. As a result, aviation services were suspended and all prepaid money was returned to the tourists. However, Austria possessed a large supply of the vaccine had a positive effect on limiting the spread of the coronavirus after a certain period. As a result, recovery began after the third wave of the pandemic, and a limited number of mass gatherings began.

Furthermore, the Austrian government's efforts and investments in IT to rejuvenate tourism, such as 3D modeling, websites, and other sorts of telecommunications, computer apps, and tourists visiting Austria during the epidemic, have paid off. The region is safe in terms of Covid, and it displays how to go there as well as the pricing.

By the way of conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic of Austria battled with innovation adoption and advancements to compensate for the economic and social harm caused by tourism and dedicated technical funds in this field of prevention.

Recommendations

Based on the facts shown above, the state of Austria has made a few broad suggestions to ensure the health of its residents and the safety of visitors entering and exiting the nation. The main piece of suggestion is physical separation, so wearing a mask, maintaining hand hygiene, taking measures if you live with or care for someone unwell.

It is also crucial that one of the strategies used to help resuscitate Austrian tourism is that everyone entering the country must provide confirmation of vaccination and that the vaccine type must be dependable, as recognized by European nations. One of the most important recommendations for the Austrian government is to reset air flights for travel with countries where quarantine regulations have been efficient, COVID-19 are using efficient control methods, and a considerable portion of the population is vaccinated.

Eliminating travel restrictions and collaborating with enterprises to get access to monetary supports, implement new health measures for safe travel, and assist in market diversification. Restoring traveler trust and driving demand with new safe and clean labels for the industry, tourist information applications, and domestic tourism promotion efforts. Creating comprehensive tourist recovery strategies to rehabilitate destinations, attract entrepreneurship and innovation.

References

- Baratti, L. (2021). *Technology's Impact on the Future of Travel Post COVID-19*. [online] Travel Pulse. Available at: <https://www.travelpulse.com/news/travel-technology/technologys-impact-on-the-future-of-travel-post-covid-19.html>.
- Fechner, I. (2020). *Covid-19's impact on the Austrian economy*. [online] ING. Available at: <https://think.ing.com/articles/covid-19-impact-on-the-austrian-economy>.
- Carlos, J. (2020). *Recommendations to prevent and manage health risks related to the transmission of COVID-19*. [online] IDB. Available at: <https://publications.iadb.org/publications/english/document/Recommendations-to-prevent-and-manage-health-risks-related-to-the-transmission-of-COVID-19-in-development-projects-funded-by-the-IDB.pdf>.
- Covax (2021). *Worldwide vaccination rate*. [online] covax. live. Available at: <https://covidvax.live/>.
- Statista Research Department (2021). *Use of cloud computing services among travel agencies, tour operators, and related activities in the European Union (EU 27) from 2016 to 2020, by cloud service*. [online] Statista. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1231753/travel-agencies-cloud-computing-services-eu/>.
- Gallagher, J. (2020). *Austria to go into full lockdown as Covid surges*. [online] BBC News. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-59343650>.
- Tchakarova, V. (2020). *The Covid-19 crisis and the Austrian response*. [online] Observer Research Foundation. Available at: <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/the-covid-19-crisis-and-the-austrian-response-64344/>.
- Statista Research Department (2020). *Austria: Unemployment rate from 1999 to 2020*. [online] Statista. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/262695/unemployment-rate-in-austria/>.

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- Yaginsu, C. (2021). *Can I Still Travel to Europe?* [online] New York Times. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/11/24/travel/europe-travel-covid-restrictions.html>.
- Worlddata Research Department (2019). *Tourism in Austria*. [online] Worlddata.info. Available at: <https://www.worlddata.info/europe/austria/tourism.php>.
- IIASA Department (2020). *Recovery of the Austrian economy following the COVID-19 crisis can take up to three years*. [online] International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis. Available at: <https://iiasa.ac.at/web/home/resources/publications/IIASAPolicyBriefs/pb26.html>.